

Numerical Analysis of a Liénard Oscillator with Fractional Order Circuit Elements

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Abstract

The Liénard oscillator is a nonlinear dynamical system governed by a differential equation that incorporates both damping and restoring terms. It is widely used in physics and engineering to model self-sustained oscillations, including electrical circuits and biological rhythms. A special case of this oscillator is the Van der Pol oscillator, which exhibits limit cycles and nonlinear behavior. The Liénard oscillator plays a crucial role in understanding complex oscillatory phenomena in both classical and quantum mechanics. In the last half century, fractional-order circuit elements have become very popular. They can be used to model electrical components, circuits, systems, etc. A Liénard oscillator can also be modified to have a fractional-order capacitor and a fractional-order inductor instead of the LTI ones. In this case, the oscillator is still nonlinear, and a numerical method should be used to solve it. Fractional-order derivatives introduce more design parameters that allow designing a more flexible Liénard oscillator with more complex dynamical behavior than one with classical integer-order derivatives or the LTI circuit elements. This article models the use of a fractional-order capacitor and a fractional-order inductor in a Liénard oscillator and examines its dynamical behavior parametrically using the Grünwald-Letnikov Fractional derivative. The performance of fractional-order circuit elements in the Liénard oscillator is evaluated considering their parameters. The results show that usage of the fractional order circuit elements results in a more complex behavior of Liénard oscillators due to having extra parameters.

Keywords: Liénard Oscillator, Fractional order capacitor, Fractional order inductor, Fractional order circuits, Fractional order derivative, Grünwald-Letnikov Fractional derivative.

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1. Introduction

The Van der Pol oscillator is among the earliest types of oscillators documented in scientific literature [1–4]. It represents a specific instance of the broader class known as Liénard oscillators [5, 6]. Due to their complexity and prevalence, they are among the most extensively researched oscillatory systems [1, 7]. These oscillators are governed by the Liénard equation, a nonlinear second-order differential equation that is frequently analyzed in academic studies [6–8]. Similar to the Van der Pol oscillator, Liénard oscillators generally do not have closed-form analytical solutions [6, 8-13]. A typical Liénard oscillator consists of a nonlinear resistor whose resistance can be positive and negative values, a negative linear time-invariant (LTI) resistor, an LTI inductor, and an LTI capacitor [9]. Although semiconductor technology was not yet developed when the Liénard Oscillator was discovered, it is now possible to create Liénard Oscillators in various structures using modern semiconductor components [14–20]. During the development of radio and vacuum tube technologies, the Liénard equations were extensively employed to model oscillatory circuits [4]. In [14], a tunnel diode-based Van der Pol Oscillator was designed, leading to microwave sources built with resonant tunneling diodes. In [16], a VDPO described by the Liénard equation was discovered using an optical resonance tunnel diode. A VDPO based on an antiparallel Schottky diode array was proposed in [17]. A Liénard Oscillator circuit topology containing a Schottky Diode Bridge rectifier and JFET at the output is proposed and suggested in [18]. The Liénard oscillator designed in [19] contains a hand-made optocoupler with a LDR combined with a negative impedance converter to obtain the necessary nonlinear resistance function. A Liénard oscillator is made with two anti-parallel connected Knowm memristors in [20]. Since they are not analytically solvable, numerical techniques are typically employed for their analysis [21-22].

Fractional-order derivatives have become extensively utilized for modeling and controlling engineering systems [23-26]. Recently, fractional-order circuit elements have gained attention as a compelling area of

research [27-31]. These derivatives are particularly effective for modeling specific types of supercapacitors [32-38]. In the literature, the studies on the circuits with fractional circuit elements have been commonly conducted using the Grünwald-Letnikov, Caputo, and Riemann–Liouville derivatives since such analyses are important from a circuit theory point of view and for their possible applications [39-43]. From a circuit theory perspective, analyzing oscillator circuits containing new types of circuit elements such as fractional capacitors and inductors is of critical importance. Fractional-order derivative approaches such as Riemann-Liouville and Caputo are usually preferred for solving differential equations [44]. However, the Grünwald-Letnikov fractional-order derivative is used for the numerical analysis of the fractional differential equations [45-46]. If there is a nonlinear circuit element in the circuit with fractional order circuit elements, the Grünwald-Letnikov fractional derivative must be employed for its solution.

Fractional order Van der Pol oscillators have become very popular in the last two decades [47-48]. By replacing the ordinary derivative(s) with a fractional derivative(s), different oscillatory behaviors are obtained [48-50].

Contrary to the integer order case, trajectories in a fractional Van der Pol oscillator may not converge to a unique limit cycle [50, 51]. The fractional order van der Pol oscillators show rich dynamics [52-56]. Fractional order generalized van der Pol systems have a tendency to show chaotic behavior [57-60]. To the best of our knowledge, a Liénard oscillator, which uses a fractional capacitor instead of an LTI capacitor and a fractional inductor instead of an LTI inductor, has not been inspected in the literature yet. Considering oscillator theory or applications, such an analysis is very important. The aim of this study is to examine a Liénard oscillator with a fractional capacitor, a fractional inductor, and a nonlinear resistor, which takes not only negative but also positive resistance values as a function of its voltage. Since such a circuit has a nonlinear resistor, it is not an LTI circuit, and it is not possible to obtain an analytical solution for its voltage. That's why the Grünwald-Letnikov fractional derivative, which is calculated numerically, is

used to simulate the oscillator instead of using fractional derivatives such as Riemann-Liouville and Caputo. Using different values of the orders of the fractional derivatives, the oscillator is simulated.

1.1 The paper is organized as follows

- ❖ Section 2: introduces the definitions of the fractional capacitor and fractional inductor;
- ❖ Section 3: derives the differential equation of the oscillator;
- ❖ Section 4: presents the Grünwald–Letnikov fractional derivative and applies it to solve the fractional-order Liénard oscillator;
- ❖ Section 5: analyzes the oscillator using this approach;
- ❖ Section 6: concludes the paper.

2. On the Fractional Order Circuit Components

The new type of Liénard Oscillator examined in this study is shown in Figure 1. It consists of a fractional order inductor L_β , a fractional order capacitor C_α , and a generic nonlinear resistor NR connected in parallel. For $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, the constitutive law of the fractional order capacitor is described by:

$$i_{C_\alpha}(t) = C_\alpha \frac{d^\alpha v_{C_\alpha}(t)}{dt^\alpha} \quad (1)$$

where $i_{C_\alpha}(t)$, $v_{C_\alpha}(t)$, C_α , and α are the fractional capacitor current, the fractional capacitor voltage, and the fractional capacitor coefficient, and the derivative order of fractional capacitor voltage, respectively.

For $\alpha = 1$, it turns into an LTI capacitor. Its well-known constitutive law is given as:

$$i_c(t) = C \frac{dv_c(t)}{dt} \quad (2)$$

The constitutive law of the fractional order inductor is described by:

$$v_{L_\beta}(t) = L_\beta \frac{d^\beta i_{L_\beta}(t)}{dt^\beta} \quad (3)$$

where $i_{L_\beta}(t)$, $v_{L_\beta}(t)$, L_β , and β are the fractional inductor current, the fractional inductor voltage, and the fractional inductor

coefficient, and the derivative order of fractional inductor current, respectively.

For $\beta = 1$, it turns into an LTI inductor. Its well-known constitutive law is given as:

$$v_L(t) = L \frac{di_L(t)}{dt} \quad (4)$$

3. The Fractional Order Oscillator Circuit

The generic Liénard oscillator is shown in Figure 1.a. It consists of an LTI inductor, an LTI capacitor, and a nonlinear resistor [9]. A Van der Pol oscillator, which is a special case of a Liénard oscillator circuit shown in Figure 1.b, is examined in [17]. The fractional order Liénard oscillator to be examined in this study possesses not only a fractional capacitor but also a fractional inductor as shown in Figure 2.

As in [17], by adjusting circuit parameters, the nonlinear resistor of the oscillator is chosen to have the characteristic:

$$i_{NL}(t) = -\mu \left(v_{NL}(t) - \frac{(v_{NL}(t))^3}{3} \right) \quad (5)$$

where $i_{NL}(t)$ and $v_{NL}(t)$ and μ are the current, voltage, and coefficient of the nonlinear resistor.

Using the KVL in the fractional order Liénard oscillator:

$$v_{L_\beta}(t) = v_{C_\alpha}(t) = v_{NL}(t) \quad (6)$$

Using the KCL in the fractional order Liénard oscillator:

$$i_{L_\beta}(t) + i_{C_\alpha}(t) + i_{NL}(t) = 0 \quad (7)$$

By substituting Eq.s (1) and (5) into Eq. (7),

$$i_{L_\beta}(t) + C_\alpha \frac{d^\alpha v_{C_\alpha}(t)}{dt^\alpha} - \mu \left(v_{C_\alpha}(t) - \frac{(v_{C_\alpha}(t))^3}{3} \right) = 0 \quad (8)$$

$$i_{L_\beta}(t) + C_\alpha \frac{d^\alpha v_{C_\alpha}(t)}{dt^\alpha} - \mu \left(1 - \frac{(v_{C_\alpha}(t))^2}{3} \right) v_{C_\alpha}(t) = 0 \quad (9)$$

By submitting Eq. (3) into Eq. (9), the following differential equation is obtained:

$$i_{L_\beta}(t) + C_\alpha \frac{d^\alpha}{dt^\alpha} \left(L_\beta \frac{d^\beta i_{L_\beta}(t)}{dt^\beta} \right) -$$

$$\mu \left(1 - \frac{\left(L_\beta \frac{d^\beta i_{L_\beta}(t)}{dt^\beta} \right)^2}{3} \right) \left(L_\beta \frac{d^\beta i_{L_\beta}(t)}{dt^\beta} \right) = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$L_\beta C_\alpha \frac{d^\alpha}{dt^\alpha} \left(\frac{d^\beta i_{L_\beta}(t)}{dt^\beta} \right) - \mu L_\beta \left(1 - \frac{\left(L_\beta \frac{d^\beta i_{L_\beta}(t)}{dt^\beta} \right)^2}{3} \right) \frac{d^\beta i_{L_\beta}(t)}{dt^\beta} + i_{L_\beta}(t) = 0 \quad (11)$$

Eq. (11) is a nonlinear differential equation. if $\alpha=\beta=1$, the equation turns into an extended

Liénard equation since $\left(1 - \frac{\left(L \frac{di_L(t)}{dt} \right)^2}{3} \right)$ is an even function:

$$L_\beta C_\alpha \frac{d^2 i_L(t)}{dt^2} - \mu L \left(1 - \frac{\left(L \frac{di_L(t)}{dt} \right)^2}{3} \right) \frac{di_L(t)}{dt} + i_L(t) = 0 \quad (12)$$

The state-space equations of the new oscillator can be written as:

$$\frac{d^\beta i_{L_\beta}(t)}{dt^\beta} = \frac{v_{C_\alpha}(t)}{L_\beta} \quad (13)$$

and

$$\frac{d^\alpha v_{C_\alpha}(t)}{dt^\alpha} = \frac{\mu}{C_\alpha} \left(v_{C_\alpha}(t) - \frac{(v_{C_\alpha}(t))^3}{3} \right) - \frac{i_{L_\beta}(t)}{C_\alpha} \quad (14)$$

Due to the nonlinearity, the circuit does not possess an analytical solution and can be solved with the Grünwald-Letnikov fractional derivative numerically.

Figure 1. a) The generic Liénard oscillator [9], and **b)** Parallel Van der Pol Oscillator Circuit Constructed Using a Back-to-Back Connected Schottky Diode Array [17].

Source: Authors.

Figure 2. The complete fractional order Liénard oscillator, possesses not only a fractional capacitor but also a fractional inductor.

Source: Authors.

4. Solution of the Oscillator Differential Equation via the Grünwald–Letnikov Fractional Derivative

Even a Van der Pol Oscillator, which is a simplified subset of the Liénard oscillator does not have an exact analytical solution. That's why a numerical solution of the fractional order Liénard oscillator is needed. In this study, by using the Grünwald-Letnikov fractional derivative, Eq.s (13) and (14) are solved simultaneously at each time step. The Grünwald-Letnikov fractional derivative direct is given as:

$$D^q f(t) = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{h^q} \sum_{0 \leq m \leq \infty} (-1)^m \binom{q}{m} f(t-mh) \quad (15)$$

The Grünwald–Letnikov derivative direct can be approximated as

$$D^q f(t) \approx \frac{1}{h^q} \sum_{0 \leq m \leq \infty} (-1)^m \binom{q}{m} f(t-mh) \quad (16)$$

Since the GL method defines derivatives as weighted sums of past values, it is highly

$$v_{C_\alpha}(t_k) = \frac{h^\alpha}{C_\alpha} \left(\mu \left(v_{C_\alpha}(t_{k-1}) - \frac{(v_{C_\alpha}(t_{k-1}))^3}{3} \right) - i_{L_\beta}(t_{k-1}) \right) - \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} c_j^{(\alpha)} v_{C_\alpha}(t_{k-j}) \quad (19)$$

and

$$i_{L_\beta}(t_k) = \frac{v_{C_\alpha}(t_{k-1})}{L_\beta} h^\beta - \sum_{j=1}^{N-1} c_j^{(\beta)} i_{L_\beta}(t_{k-j}) \quad (20)$$

5. Simulations

In this section, the simulation results of the fractional-order oscillator are presented.

Each subsystem was numerically solved using the Euler–Grünwald–Letnikov (Euler–GL) framework, which incorporates memory effects through fractional-order derivatives expressed via binomial coefficients. The discrete-time formulations given in Equations (19) and (20) were implemented in MATLAB, where the binomial coefficients were computed using the gamma function as defined in Equation (18). To investigate the oscillator's dynamic behavior, the parameters, μ , α and β

effective in systems that incorporate memory effects. In [61], the solution of Grünwald–Letnikov derivative is given as

$$f(t_k) = w(t_{k-1}) h^q - \sum_{j=1}^{N-1} c_j^{(q)} f(t_{k-j}) \quad (17)$$

where $f(t_k)$ is the value of the function $f(t)$ at k^{th} time step, $f(t_{k-j})$ is the value of the function $f(t)$ at $(k-j)^{\text{th}}$ time step, $w(t_{k-1})$ is value of the fractional derivative at $(1)^{\text{th}}$ time step, h is the time step, q is the order of the fractional derivative, $c_j^{(q)}$ is j^{th} Binomial coefficients, N is the number of previous values of the function.

The Binomial coefficient for j^{th} previous value of the function $f(t)$ is calculated as

$$c_j^{(q)} = (-1)^j \frac{\Gamma(q+1)}{\Gamma(j+1) \cdot \Gamma(q-j+1)} \quad (18)$$

Adapting Eq. (17) to solve the state-space equations of the fractional order Liénard oscillator, the fractional capacitor voltage and the fractional inductor current at the k^{th} time step is expressed as follows:

were systematically varied, enabling control over the voltage waveform shape. The graph in Figure 3 illustrates the response of a system constructed with integer order capacitor and inductor elements, i.e., $\alpha=1$ and $\beta=1$. No fractional effects are present in such a circuit; the system behaves like a classical Liénard oscillator or a Van der Pol Oscillator.

For certain parameter selections, the circuit fails to sustain oscillatory behavior. As an example, Figure 4 illustrates the response of the fractional-order oscillator comprising a fractional capacitor and a fractional inductor with parameters $\alpha=0.6$, $\beta=0.6$, $L_\beta =$

$1.0 H/s^{1-\beta}$, $C_\infty = 1.0 F/s^{1-\alpha}$, and $\mu = 1.0$. Under these conditions, oscillations are not maintained: the oscillator voltage and

component currents gradually decay to zero, and no limit cycle emerges. Consequently, all state variables asymptotically converge to the origin.

Figure 3. The capacitor voltage, the inductor current, the capacitor current and the limit cycle of the oscillator for $\alpha=1.0$, $\beta = 1.0$, $L_\beta=1.0 H$, $C_\infty = 1.0 F$, and $\mu = 1.0$.

Source: Authors.

Figure 4. The capacitor voltage, the inductor current, and the capacitor current of the oscillator for $\alpha = 0.6$, $\beta = 0.6$, $L_\beta= 1.0 H/s^{1-\beta}$, $C_\infty = 1.0 F/s^{1-\alpha}$, and $\mu = 1.0$.

Source: Authors.

For certain parameter values, the circuit exhibits chaotic oscillations. As an illustrative case, Figure 5 shows the response of the fractional-order oscillator with parameters $\alpha=0.3$, $\beta=0.8$, $L_\beta=1.0 \text{ H/s}^{1-\beta}$, $C_\alpha = 1.0 \text{ F/s}^{1-\alpha}$, and $\mu = 6.5$. The relatively large value of μ

amplifies the influence of the nonlinear element, thereby dominating the system dynamics. Under these conditions, the oscillations are non-periodic: the voltage and current waveforms display irregular, chaotic behavior, and no unique limit cycle is formed.

Figure 5. The capacitor voltage, the inductor current, and the capacitor current of the oscillator for $\alpha = 0.3$, $\beta = 0.8$, $L_\beta=1.0 \text{ H/s}^{1-\beta}$, $C_\alpha = 1.0 \text{ F/s}^{1-\alpha}$, and $\mu = 6.5$.

Source: Authors.

Figure 6 illustrates the oscillator response under the parameter set, $\alpha = 0.5$, $\beta = 0.5$, $L_\beta=1.0 \text{ H/s}^{1-\beta}$, $C_\alpha = 1.0 \text{ F/s}^{1-\alpha}$, and $\mu = 1.5$. In this case, the oscillator voltage and current waveforms exhibit a more sinusoidal-like periodic form, accompanied by stable oscillations. The relatively low value of μ weakens the effect of the nonlinear resistance, allowing the system dynamics to approach sinusoidal behavior. Consequently, the oscillator operates in a periodic regime.

Figure 7 presents the circuit response for the parameter set $\alpha = 0.3$, $\beta = 0.3$, $L_\beta=1.0 \text{ H/s}^{1-\beta}$, $C_\alpha = 1.0 \text{ F/s}^{1-\alpha}$, and $\mu = 0.3$. The very low fractional orders of the capacitor and inductor render the system highly dissipative, leading to rapid energy loss. As a result, oscillations are almost completely suppressed: the voltage and current waveforms decay to zero, no limit cycle is established, and

all state variables asymptotically converge to the origin.

Figure 8 depicts the oscillator response for the parameter set $\alpha = 0.8$, $\beta = 0.8$, $L_\beta=1.0 \text{ H/s}^{1-\beta}$, $C_\alpha = 1.0 \text{ F/s}^{1-\alpha}$, and $\mu = 4$. The relatively high value of μ enhances the influence of the nonlinear resistance, thereby shaping the system dynamics. Under these conditions, the oscillator voltage and current waveforms are periodic and closely resemble those of an integer-order Van der Pol oscillator or an integer-order Liénard oscillator. Also, the oscillator has a unique limit cycle.

Figure 9 presents the circuit response for the parameter set $\alpha = 0.5$, $\beta = 0.5$, $L_\beta=1.0 \text{ H/s}^{1-\beta}$, $C_\alpha = 1.0 \text{ F/s}^{1-\alpha}$, and $\mu = 3.0$. The intermediary fractional orders of the capacitor and inductor render the system highly dissipative, leading to rapid energy loss. As a result, oscillations are almost completely

suppressed: the voltage and current waveforms settle down to constant values.

Figure 6. The capacitor voltage, the inductor current, and the capacitor current of the oscillator for $\alpha=0.5$, $\beta = 0.5$, $L_\beta=1.0 H/s^{1-\beta}$, $C_\alpha = 1.0 F/s^{1-\alpha}$, and $\mu = 1.5$.

Source: Authors.

Figure 7. The capacitor voltage, the inductor current, and the capacitor current of the oscillator, for $\alpha = 0.3$, $\beta = 0.3$, $L_\beta=1.0 H/s^{1-\beta}$, $C_\alpha = 1.0 F/s^{1-\alpha}$, and $\mu = 0.3$.

Source: Authors.

For certain parameter values, the circuit exhibits chaotic oscillations. As an illustrative case, Figure 5 shows the response of the fractional-order oscillator with parameters $\alpha=0.3$, $\beta = 0.3$, $L_\beta=1.0 H/s^{1-\beta}$, $C_\alpha = 1.0 F/s^{1-\alpha}$, and $\mu = 7.0$. The relatively large value of μ amplifies the influence of the nonlinear element, thereby

dominating the system dynamics. Under these conditions, the oscillations are non-periodic: the voltage and current waveforms display irregular, chaotic behavior, and no unique limit cycle is formed. It is interesting that the oscillator waveforms have non-zero average values, and the limit cycle does not occur around the origin.

Figure 8 The capacitor voltage, the inductor current, and the capacitor current of the oscillator, for $\alpha = 0.8$, $\beta = 0.8$, $L_\beta = 1.0 \text{ H/s}^{1-\beta}$, $C_\alpha = 1.0 \text{ F/s}^{1-\alpha}$, and $\mu = 4$.

Source: Authors.

Figure 9 The capacitor voltage, the inductor current, and the capacitor current of the oscillator, for $\alpha = 0.5$, $\beta = 0.5$, $L_\beta = 1.0 \text{ H/s}^{1-\beta}$, $C_\alpha = 1.0 \text{ F/s}^{1-\alpha}$, and $\mu = 3.0$.

Source: Authors.

Figure 10 The capacitor voltage, the inductor current, and the capacitor current of the oscillator, for $\alpha = 0.3$, $\beta = 0.3$, $L_\beta = 1.0 \text{ H/s}^{1-\beta}$, $C_\alpha = 1.0 \text{ F/s}^{1-\alpha}$, and $\mu = 7.0$

Source: Authors.

For the parameters' values, α ranging from 0.1 to 1, β ranging from 0.1 to 1, and μ for 0.5, 1, 2, 5, and 10, the simulations have been performed and parametric maps showing the circuits' behavior have been obtained and shown in Figures 11-15. The parametric maps demonstrate that the onset and extent of oscillatory regions depend non-monotonically on μ .

Figure 11 Oscillatory Regions for $\mu = 1.0$.

Source: Authors.

Figure 12 Oscillatory Regions for $\mu = 0.5$.

Source: Authors.

At low values of μ , oscillations are rare and confined to narrow parameter bands; at intermediate values, oscillatory domains expand significantly; and at high values, oscillations become restricted again, requiring large β . This progression highlights the critical interplay between μ and β , underscoring the importance of parameter tuning for achieving or suppressing oscillatory behavior in practical applications.

Figure 13 Oscillatory Regions for $\mu = 2$.

Source: Authors.

Figure 14 Oscillatory Regions for $\mu = 5$.

Source: Authors.

Figure 15. Oscillatory Regions for $\mu = 10$.

Source: Authors.

Taken together, Figures 11–15 reveal a non-monotonic dependence of oscillatory behavior on μ . At low μ , oscillations are rare and confined to narrow parameter bands; at intermediate μ ,

oscillatory regions expand dramatically, lowering the threshold for oscillation onset; and at high μ , oscillations become restricted again, requiring large values of β . This progression underscores the delicate interplay between μ and β , demonstrating that oscillatory regimes are not simply scaled with μ but instead undergo qualitative shifts in accessibility.

This systematic evolution across μ values provides a clear framework for understanding how parameters influence oscillatory dynamics. The findings directly inform stability analysis and parameter selection, offering practical guidance for designing systems where oscillatory behavior must be either harnessed for functionality or suppressed to ensure robustness.

6. Conclusions

In this paper, a Liénard oscillator made with a FO inductor and FO capacitor is examined for the first time in the literature. The Grünvald-Letnikov fractional derivative is used in the simulations, which has confirmed that the circuit operates as a Liénard Oscillator. It has been shown that varying the orders of the circuit elements can be used to tune the shape of the waveforms. It has been also realized that improper selection of fractional parameters does not result in oscillation. It has also been shown that the circuit shows chaotic behavior for some regions of the parameters. The coupling of the Van der Pol or Liénard Oscillators with the other oscillators is currently a hot research topic, and we suggest coupling of this oscillator with other oscillators is also suggested as future work. Also, it should be examined that the chaotic behavior of the coupling of this oscillator with a sinusoidal source can also be examined by changing either the magnitude or frequency of the sinusoidal source parametrically.

Author Contribution

Formal analysis –Reşat Mutlu (RM), Nisanur Durukan (ND), Irem Batıbey (IB); Investigation – RM, ND, IB; Data Collection – ND, IB; Processing – RM, ND, IB; Literature review – RM; Writing – RM; Review and editing – RM, ND, IB.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declared no conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration Of Ethical Standards

The author(s) of this article declare that the materials and methods used in this study do not require ethical committee permission and/or legal-special permission.

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